

USE OF TRADITIONAL AND NON-TRADITIONAL METHODS IN PRIMARY MOTHER TONGUE CLASSES

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Abstract. The article describes the meaning and importance of using various interesting games in the primary language and reading lessons, as well as the activities of working with students.

Keywords: education, method, lesson, process, technology, teacher.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, modern teaching methods are widely used in the educational process. The use of modern teaching methods leads to high efficiency in the teaching process. When choosing educational methods, it is appropriate to choose based on the didactic task of each lesson. While preserving the traditional form of the lesson, enriching it with methods that activate the activities of various learners will lead to an increase in the level of mastery of learners. For this purpose, the lesson process should be organized rationally, the teacher should increase the interest of the learners and encourage their activity in the educational process, divide the educational material into small parts and open their content intellectually. It is necessary to use methods such as attack, working in small groups, debate, problem situation, guiding text, project, role-playing and encouraging learners to do practical exercises independently. These methods are also called interactive or interactive methods.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Interactive methods mean methods that activate learners and encourage

them to think independently, with the learner at the center of the educational process. When these methods are used, the teacher invites the learner to actively participate. The learner is involved throughout the process. Benefits of a learner-centered approach include:

- study-study with higher educational efficiency;*
- high motivation of the learner;*
- consideration of previously acquired knowledge;*
- adjustment of the intensity of study to the needs of the learner;*
- support of the learner's initiative and responsibility;*
- learning by doing;*
- creation of conditions for two-way feedback.*

Here are some examples of games for elementary school students.

RESULTS

Ability is important in the formation of professional skills of a teacher. Because pedagogical skills are based on the educational and educational relationship that should be implemented with the student. It is the continuous and stable nature of this relationship that gives rise to a certain pedagogical technology. The main goal and task of the new pedagogical technology is aimed at learning, generalizing and popularizing new methodological skills. In short, the emergence of knowledge and abilities is the amalgamation of the teacher's creativity, the application of new pedagogical technology based on his professional skills.

For this, the teacher should work on himself, constantly search for new methods of education, use instructional tools, technical tools, handouts, and test questions effectively in the teaching process. It is necessary to organize lessons based on the requirements of DTS, pedagogical technology methods in the form of lesson-scenario, lesson-conversation, lesson-excursion. I think that the organization of classes based on nationality, non-traditional classes, and non-

standard classes depends on the ability and skills of the teacher.

The innovative activity of the teacher depends on a number of conditions, the clash of different views and the effective implementation of mutually rich activities. It includes teacher's appropriate communication, impartial attitude towards opposing opinions, readiness to show recognition of rational situation in various situations. As a result, the teacher will have a common topic (motive) that will provide his knowledge and scientific activity.

Themes (motives) such as self-activation, creativity, self-knowledge and creativity are of great importance in the activity of a teacher. This gives an opportunity to form the creativity of the teacher.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

An important condition for innovation is to create a new situation of communication. The new situation of communication is the teacher's position of independence, to the world, is the ability to create a new attitude towards pedagogical science and oneself. A teacher does not get stuck in his views, he opens up and improves through rich forms of pedagogical experiences. In such situations, the teacher's ways of thinking, intellectual culture change, and emotional feelings develop.

The next condition is the teacher's readiness for culture and communication.

The innovative activity of the teacher is aimed at changing reality, identifying its problems and ways to solve them.

A change in the pattern of communication between a teacher and a student is one of the conditions for innovative activity.

New relationships, as in traditions, should be free of elements such as demands, submission to judgment. They should be built in the form of cooperation of equals, mutual management, mutual support. The most important feature of their relationship is the creative cooperation of the teacher and the student.

Innovative activity is explained by the following main functions:

- conscious analysis of professional activity;
- critical approach to standards;
- readiness for professional innovations;
- to have a creative attitude to the world;
- (realization of one's potential, embodiment of one's lifestyle and aspirations in professional activity).

Therefore, the teacher appears as the author, developer, researcher, user and promoter of new pedagogical technologies, theories, concepts.

In the conditions of current society, culture and educational development, the need for teacher innovation activity is measured by:

- socio-economic renewal requires a fundamental renewal of the educational system, methodology and technology of the educational process.
- in such conditions, the teacher's innovative activity consists of creating, mastering and using pedagogical innovations;
- humanization of content, requires constant search for new organizational forms and technologies of teaching;
- change in the nature of the teacher's attitude towards mastering pedagogical innovation and its implementation.

The analysis of the teacher's innovative activity requires the use of certain standards that determine the effectiveness of innovation. Such standards include novelty, optimality, high efficiency, and the possibility of creative application of innovation in public experiments.

Newness reflects the essence of the newness, the level of novelty offered in itself as a standard of pedagogical innovation. Pedagogical scientists distinguish the absolute, limited absolute, conditional, subjective levels of innovation, which differ according to the level and field of application of innovation.

The standard of acceptability indicates the effort and means used by the

teacher and the student to achieve the result.

Effectiveness refers to certain important positive results in the teacher's activity.

CONCLUSIONS

Using advanced methods to develop students' reading skills and develop speech. Logical methods that direct students to independent thinking are reflected in interactive methods. Teaching methods are a means of organizing the teacher's activities. Teaching and learning methods that give education a discussion and developing character, and ensure productive activity of learners are called interactive methods. Here are some examples of such interactive methods and technologies: Presentations and discussions are short exercises designed to start the training. A method aimed at removing the "barrier" between the teacher and the learner. This method is based on teaching students to feel mutual trust, respect, and closeness.

Brainstorming or brainstorming is based on this method, a specific problem through the rapid movement of the mind within a limited time.

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